

Semitheoretical INDO Calculation of Activation Energy of Base Hydrolyses of Esters in Solution. Part-I : A Model Ester in Aqueous Medium

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The calculation of activation energy of the hydrolysis of a model ester, namely, ethyl formate, in aqueous medium has been accomplished by employing (i) the INDO SCF MO method, (ii) a suitable reaction cycle and (iii) a method for calculation of hydration energies of gas phase ions and molecules. The INDO elements which figure in the evolution of the calculation technique are the geometry optimisation, binding energies (incidentally modified) and the net molecular orbital charge distributions at the atoms. This semitheoretical calculation is remarkable from two viewpoints. In the first place, it shows the way for treating activation energies of reactions in solution i.e. in condensed phase and in the second, it serves as the potential "take-off" base for calculation of activation energies of hydrolyses of more complex esters, a theme dealt with successfully in a separate communication.

ORGANIC reactions of any particular mechanism are often characterised by approximately the same value of activation energy. Substitutions by homologues or substituents at positions away from the mechanistically important reaction zones only cause peripheral or minor changes in the activation energy. Quite an appreciable change is, however, observed if solvent media of different dielectric constants are employed.

To quote an instance, the alkaline hydrolyses of, say, ethyl esters of aliphatic and aromatic acids, usually involve $B_{AC}2$ mechanism (acyl oxygen scission) with experimental activation energy value lying in the range 11 to 18 kcal/mol approximately. The tackling of such a problem, theoretically or even semitheoretically, encounters heavy odds due to the following reasons :

(1). It is almost impossible to compute the complete potential energy surface for such a reaction system comprising the ester and OH^- ions, owing to inordinately large³ number of degrees of freedom. The configuration of the activated complex thus eludes us.

(2). Although powerful theoretical or semi-theoretical quantum mechanical tools exist for dealing with molecular systems, their applications have mostly been restricted to gas phase molecules and ions, while ester hydrolysis takes place in solution.

(3). The passage¹ from the gas phase state (amenable to quantum mechanical treatment) to solution state is not fully explored because the theoretical techniques for treating hydration energies of ions and molecules, except for very simple ions, lack practical feasibility.

In this paper (which is Part I of a two paper series), we take ethyl formate as our illustrative model ester and carve out a way, based on (i) Born-Haber type of cycle, (ii) INDO SCF MO method⁴ and (iii) a recent paper⁵ dealing successfully with hydration energy problem of gas phase polyatomic ions and molecules to assess the activation energy of hydrolysis. This skirts the difficulty presented by (1) above, but still finds the activated complex configuration from a limited exploration of potential energy surface.

Method :

Consider the preceding cycle involving two paths, each of which culminates in the hydrolysis of ethyl formate finally.

The cycle demonstrates two paths for the generation of activated complex in aqueous solution. Path I is the conventional one followed in experimental studies with

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta H_1 &= \text{Enthalpy of } \uparrow \text{ reaction (upto the activation stage)} \\ &= \text{Experimental activation energy } (\Delta E). \end{aligned}$$

Path II is an alternative hypothetical gas phase route for producing the precursor (gas phase activated complex) which on hydration yields the real activated complex in solution. Evidently, activation energy

$$\Delta E = \Delta H_1 = -\Delta H_{hy}(M) - \Delta H_{hy}(OH^-) + \Delta H_a + \Delta H_{hy}(\text{precursor}) \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_{hy} represents enthalpy of hydration, M within parenthesis stands for model ester viz., ethyl formate, ΔH_a = enthalpy of activation for producing the precursor.

The energy problem thus reduces to two parts :

- Calculation of enthalpy change, ΔH_a , of the hypothetical gas phase transformation.
- Calculation of enthalpies of hydration of the three species as reflected in equation (1).

Part (A) of the energy problem needs to be completed in two stages—a determination of the configuration of the 'precursor' (viz., gas phase activated complex), followed by calculation of ΔH_a , which is incidentally the binding energy difference of the 'precursor' and of the gas phase reactants, ester and OH^- ion. These two phases of calculations are accomplished by using SCF INDO molecular orbital method.

Search for configuration of the 'precursor' :

Following the cue of the transition state in solution⁴ (B_{Ac2} mechanism), we start with a thirteen atom (charged) 'precursor' (Fig. 1) of the ester $-OH^-$ adduct in which the atoms are numbered.

The bond distances $d_{C-O(9-10)}$, $d_{C-O(9-12)}$, $d_{O-H(12-13)}$, $d_{C-O(9-1)}$ and the stereochemical angles at C(9) are significant in as much as these constitute the reaction zone. The other bond distances and angles in the $-CH_2-CH_3$ unit are taken to be the same as are found in standard tables and kept frozen at their equilibrium values in course of the search for the precursor configuration. The $d_{C-H(9-11)}$ bond distance between carboxy C and H is fixed at 1.47 Å both in the precursor as well as in the model ester instead of at 1.1 Å as found in ethyl formate. This is done with a view to making the final formulation for the activation energy of the model ester as the 'take-off' ground for further calculations with other esters where the H atom no. 11

Fig. 1. The precursor.

is substituted by phenyl, cinnamyl or their substituted varieties to give rise to benzoate or cinnamate esters. The normal distance between the carboxy C and the aryl C is 1.47 Å.

The search for geometrical characteristics of the precursor is made in three laps, the first two being tentative. The first is a calculation with different trial configurations and has the objective of narrowing down the area of search for the bond distances in the reaction zone of the precursor. The second is to draw some inferences from a simulated BEP analysis⁵. The final lap is the optimisation of the stereochemical angle at carbon atom no. 9 and to decide, additionally, the bond distances in the precursor.

First lap : Many INDO MO calculations are made starting initially with the model proposed by Laidler and Landskroener⁴ for solution phase. This is characterised by $d_{O-H(12-13)} = 1.76$ Å, $d_{C-O(9-12)} = 1.43$ Å, $d_{C-O(9-1)} = 2.15$ Å and the stereochemical angle at C(9) being $109^\circ 28'$. A series of variations of $d_{C-O(9-1)}$ from 2.15 Å causes a fall in the INDO energy value from -77.9660 a.u. to a minimum of -78.3220 a.u. at 1.35 Å. A second set of INDO calculations with some trial distance values around the equilibrium values of such bonds viz., $d_{O-H(12-13)} = 0.97$ Å, $d_{C-O(9-12)} = 1.35$ Å and the stereochemical angle at C(9) = $109^\circ 28'$, are made while permitting a variation of $d_{C-O(9-1)}$. This yields an energy minimum of -78.4427 a.u. at $d_{C-O(9-1)} = 1.75$ Å. This result tentatively suggests the probable importance of an (O-H) parameter, $d_{O-H(12-13)} = 0.97$ Å, for almost similar parameter values of $d_{C-O(9-12)}$ lying in the domain of 1.35 ~ 1.43 Å. This, however, leaves us guessing as to the significant neighbourhood of the $d_{C-O(9-1)}$ value of the precursor, viz., whether it is in the vicinity of 1.35 Å or of 1.75 Å.

Second lap : A Bell-Evans-Polanyi (BEP)⁵ scheme of analysis, permissible for three-atom reaction $A+B-C \rightleftharpoons A..B..C \rightleftharpoons A-B+C$ and a three-atom transition state, is adopted for our system to help arrive at a decision on the stereochemical angle at C(9) and on the distance parameters $d_{C-O(9-1)}$ and $d_{C-O(9-12)}$.

where OH⁻, HCO⁺ and OEt⁻ are assumed to play the role of single atoms A, B and C, respectively implying that the internal degrees of freedom and the bond distances in each species are all frozen. During BEP simulation, total energy of the system (A + B - C) as obtained by INDO molecular orbital calculation is plotted as a function of the bond distance d_{B-C} i.e., the HCO-OEt bond length. The resulting curve POQ is shown in Fig. 2. A similar plot MON (Fig. 2) is made of the total energy as a function of the bond distance d_{A-B}, i.e., the HCO-OH bond length. The transition state characteristics (the distances d_{A-B} and d_{B-C}) are divulged by the distance coordinates of the point of intersection, O, of the curves POQ and MON.

Fig. 2. The BEF plot.

- — SCF points.
- — Non-SCF points with energy values obtained after 1st diagonalisation.

As is evident from the figure, some of the points in regions of high extensions of the bonds are characterised by non-attainability of self consistent INDO energy values*. Extension of curves comprising self consistent energy values intersect at O'. Both O and O' correspond to d_{B-C} and d_{A-B} lengths, 2.48 Å and 2.62 Å, respectively.

One would, therefore, be tempted to accept 2.48 Å and 2.62 Å as the parameter values of

* Attainment of self-consistency is not invariably possible in the ONDO/INDO methods when the molecular configurations are greatly distorted from their equilibrium parameter values. In the search of transition states, since such tentative distortions from equilibrium values are unavoidable, the non-SCF energy values as obtained after first diagonalisation of the Fock matrix are recorded only where the computer run faces such non-attainability of self consistency.

d_{C-O(9-1)} and d_{C-O(9-12)} in the 'precursor' molecule. But caution is to be exercised on two grounds: (a) the simplifying assumption of the conglomerate of atoms acting as single pseudo atoms wherein all the degrees of freedom remain frozen. This suggests that the ratio of the values (2.62 : 2.48 i.e. 1.056 : 1) may be more meaningful rather than the absolute values in the idealised state; (b) the precursor molecule as obtained from BEP analysis also needs optimisation with respect to stereochemical angle at C(9). An attempt at optimisation of the stereochemical angle at carbon atom no. 9 by INDO technique yields Table 1, which indicates that the optimum

TABLE 1—OPTIMISATION OF STEREOCHEMICAL ANGLE OF CARBON ATOM NUMBER 9

Angle (between C-O(9-12) bond and any of the remaining bonds of the carbonyl C(no. 9) e.g. ∠O ¹ C ⁹ O ¹²)	INDO Energy (a.u.)
109°28'	-77.41995*
105°	-77.46230*
100°	-77.49512*
95°	-77.51401*
90°	-77.50811*

* Non-SCF first diagonalisation values.

value is 95° contrary to the conventional acceptance of a tetrahedral angle for the transition state.

Third lap: The third and final lap in ascertaining the configuration of precursor is based on the suggestive data obtained in the previous two laps. A set of INDO calculated energy values for configurations with changing values of d_{C-O(9-1)} and d_{C-O(9-12)} are presented in Table 2 to settle the issue.

It is seen that the configuration of the precursor corresponding to the minimum of energy (-78.56059 a.u.) is one with d_{O-H(12-13)} = 0.97 Å, d_{C-O(9-12)} = 1.45 Å, d_{C-O(9-1)} = 1.34 Å, ∠O¹C⁹O¹² = ∠O¹C⁹O¹³ = ∠H¹¹C⁹O¹² = 95° and the rest of the bond distances and bond angles are the same as the corresponding equilibrium values in the model ester and in OH⁻ ion as stated before. It is highly satisfying to note that d_{C-O(9-12)}/d_{C-O(9-1)} = 1.45/1.34 i.e. 1.08, a figure very near to 1.056 suggested by BEP analysis.

Estimation of ΔH₂:

The second stage of Part A of the energy problem is an estimation of ΔH₂, the hypothetical gas phase activation energy. ΔH₂ can be obtained by subtracting the sum total of the INDO SCF binding energies of the model ester and the hydroxyl ion from that of the 'precursor'. The calculated binding energies should, however, be modified by the relation⁶

$$E_T = \rho'_E \cdot E(\text{INDO}) \quad \dots (2)$$

to obtain the true binding energy E_T. The modification factor, ρ'_E, is equal to 0.45 for the

TABLE 2—SCF-INDO ENERGY VALUE FOR DIFFERENT CONFIGURATIONS OF PRECURSOR

$$d_{O-H(12-13)} = 0.97 \text{ \AA}; \angle O^1CO^1 = \angle O^2CO^1 = \angle H^1CO^1 = 95^\circ$$

$d_{C-O(9-1)}$ (\AA)	$d_{C-O(9-12)}$ (\AA)						
	2.62	1.50	1.45	1.40	1.35	1.30	1.20
2.90				-78.17621	-78.17753	-78.16622	
2.70				-78.18568	-78.18680	-78.17531	
2.48	-77.51401*			-78.20536	-78.20606		-78.11802
2.15			-78.25984	-78.26887	-78.26821	-78.25494	
1.90		-78.38802	-78.35252	-78.35972	-78.35714		
1.60			-78.50393	-78.50774	-78.50150		
1.34		-78.55323	-78.56059	-78.56014			
1.30		-78.53937	-78.54594	-78.54466			

* Non-SCF first diagonalisation value.

precursor which is devoid of resonance. For the model ester, which possesses resonance, somewhat lower value is expected for ρ'_E . Three trial values, 0.44, 0.435 and 0.43, all lying within the optimal zone⁶ of 0.45 ± 0.03 are attempted. A reliable binding energy value of OH^- ion is, however, obtained by a thermochemical cycle method⁷. The binding energies of the three species and the ΔH_2 values, calculated therefrom, are shown in Table 3.

 TABLE 3—BINDING ENERGIES OF MODEL ESTER, HYDROXYL ION AND PRECURSOR AND ΔH_2

Molecule/ Species	INDO binding energy (a.u.)	True binding energy (Modified by eqn. 2 or calculated otherwise) (a.u.)	ΔH_2 (a.u.)
Model ester	-3.92793	-1.72829 ($\rho'_E = 0.44$) -1.70865 ($\rho'_E = 0.435$)	+0.01223 N* -0.00741 N
Hydroxyl ion	-0.12399	-1.68901 ($\rho'_E = 0.43$) -0.2677 (By thermochemical cycle)	-0.02705 N
Precursor	-4.40836	-1.98376 ($\rho'_E = 0.45$)	

* N = Avogadro Number.

The appropriate selection of ΔH_2 , from amongst these three, will finally be made by comparing the calculated activation energy with the normally observed experimental values.

Calculation of solvation energies :

Part B of the energy problem refers to enthalpies of hydration of the gas phase ions. The hydration energy terms appearing in equation (1) are calculated following the line of argument of a recent communication⁸. For solvation energy of a species, the following relation is used :

$$\Delta H_{\text{solv'n}} = N \left[\sum_i \frac{q_i^2}{2R_i} + \sum_i \sum_{j < i} \frac{q_i q_j}{R_{ij}} \right] \left(\frac{1}{D} - 1 \right) + 7.5 |Z| \quad \dots (3)$$

The net charges q_i, q_j on the respective atoms are computed by INDO technique. R_i and R_{ij} are the modified radii and interatomic distances in solution. In aqueous solution, $R_i = r_i + 0.5 r_w$ for charged species e.g. the precursor and the hydroxyl ion, while $R_i = r_i + r_w$ for the uncharged model ester, r_w being the radius of water molecule. Correspondingly, $R_{ij} = r_{ij} + r_w$ and $R_{ij} = r_{ij} + 2r_w$ for charged and uncharged species⁸, respectively. N and D represent the Avogadro number and the dielectric constant of the medium. $|Z|$ is the net charge of the species. Since in the final calculation, $7.5 |Z|$ terms for the precursor and the hydroxyl ion cancel mutually and since the ester carries no net charge, this term effectively makes no contribution in this particular case towards activation energy computation. The relevant data for the three species appear in Tables 4 and 5.

TABLE 4—CHARGE DISTRIBUTIONS AND RADII VALUES IN GAS PHASE

Species in Gas Phase	Atom	Tag no.	Radius (r_i) (\AA)	INDO-SCF net charge (electronic charge)
Precursor	O	1	0.66	-0.370602
	C	2	0.789	0.282754
	H	3	0.30	-0.065002
	H	4	0.30	-0.053251
	C	5	0.806	0.020541
	H	6	0.30	-0.039640
	H	7	0.30	-0.029404
	H	8	0.30	-0.025317
	C	9	0.70	0.651927
	O	10	0.66	-0.699589
	H*	11	0.74	-0.363964
	O	12	0.67	-0.428958
	H	13	0.30	0.060506
Ethyl formate (Model)	O	1	0.66	-0.2649
	C	2	0.789	0.2669
	H	3	0.30	-0.0399
	H	4	0.30	-0.0399
	C	5	0.806	0.0162
	H	6	0.30	-0.0008
	H	7	0.30	-0.0021
	H	8	0.30	-0.0021
	C	9	0.687	0.5025
	O	10	0.55	-0.3268
	H*	11	0.74	-0.1089
Hydroxyl ion	O	12	0.67	-0.8808
	H	13	0.30	-0.1192

TABLE 6—HEAT OF ACTIVATION OF BASE HYDROLYSIS OF MODEL ETHYL FORMATE
(Aqueous medium $D=78.5$; N =Avogadro number)

ΔH_2 (a.u./mole)	$\Delta H_{Hydrn}(\text{ester})$ (a.u./mole)	$\Delta H_{Hydrn}(\text{OH}^-)$ (a.u./mole)	$\Delta H_{Hydrn}(\text{precursor})$ (a.u./mole)	Heat of activation	
				$\Delta H^\ddagger(M)/w$ a.u./mole	k cal/mole
-0.02705 N	-0.03096 N	-0.18515 N	-0.18353 N	0.553×10^{-3} N	3.47
-0.00741 N	"	"	"	2.517×10^{-3} N	15.78
+0.01223 N	"	"	"	4.481×10^{-3} N	28.09

TABLE 5—DIMENSION IN HYDRATED STATE AND CORRESPONDING HYDRATION ENERGIES

Hydrated species	Atom	Tag no.	$(D=78.5; r_w=1.25\text{\AA})$		R_{ij} (internally computed) (\AA)
			$R_i = r_i + r_w$ (\AA)	INDO hydration energy per molecule or ion (a. u.)	
			p=0.5		
	O	1	1.285		
	C	2	1.414		
Hydrated 'precursor' molecule	H	3	0.925		
	H	4	0.925		
i.e.	C	5	1.431		
	H	6	0.925	-0.18353	$r_{ij} + r_w$
The transition state in solution	H	7	0.925		
	H	8	0.925		
	C	9	1.325		
	O	10	1.285		
	H*	11	1.365		
	O	12	1.295		
	H	13	0.925		
			p=1.0		
	O	1	1.91		
	C	2	2.039		
	H	3	1.55		
	H	4	1.55		
Hydrated ethyl formate (Model)	O	5	2.056		
	H	6	1.55	-0.03096	$r_{ij} + 2r_w$
	H	7	1.55		
	H	8	1.55		
	C	9	1.937		
	O	10	1.80		
	H*	11	1.99		
			p=0.5		
Hydrated hydroxyl ion	O	12	1.295	-0.18515	$r_{ij} + r_w$
	H	13	0.925		

Final calculation of activation energy :

Picking up necessary values of ΔH_2 and the hydration energies from Tables 3 and 5, the hypothetical activation energy of the base hydrolysis of the model ester in aqueous medium is computed by equation (1) and the result is shown in Table 6.

The activation energy values, although individually differ from each other, represent quite a degree of success of the parameterised semitheoretical SCF molecular orbital method. The values

obtained are remarkable, especially when considered against the background of the none-too-happy position of the general results of quantum calculations of activation energy in solution phase although quite encouraging results are obtainable in gas phase reactions^{9,10}. The calculated value of 15.78 kcal/g mole as the heat of activation for the base hydrolysis of the 'model ethyl formate' seems to fit best with the experimental activation energies for base hydrolyses of different esters lying in the range 11.0~18.0 kcal/g mole. In the present set of calculations two strong attributes (geometry and charge distribution) and one weak feature (binding energy), the latter incidentally improved empirically⁶, of the INDO SCF molecular orbital method have been used. Until the time a good theoretical method becomes available for improving the precision of the INDO energy value, the present approach, may perhaps, rightfully claim attention from the kineticists. And when the desirable precision in INDO energy value is reached, this approach will be even more powerful.

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